

LITERARY DISCOURSE AND ANALYSIS OF ITS CATEGORIES

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Abstract. Discourse is a broader concept than text, and consists of both the linguistic process and the text resulting from this process. The word "discourse" is based on the understanding of all cognitive and communicative functions of speech. It is clear that discourse is both a process and a text. The interpretation of the text as a stable, complete product and discourse as a continuous process of verbal communication makes them very different. In linguistic literature, the term "discourse" has no definite meaning, it is used to describe a wide range of events, from "part of the text" to the entire "speech".

Key words: discourse, text, discourse analysis, communication

Discourse is the subject of interdisciplinary research, as from theoretical linguistics to AI, psychology, philosophy and logic, sociology, antropology and ethnology, literature, semiotics, history, theology, law, pedagogy, translation theory and practice, politics and other discourse. It is also the main object of study of related science and research fields. Each of these disciplines approaches the study of discourse in its own way. According to the modern approaches to the notion, discourse is complex communicative phenomenon that needs extra linguistic factors such as thoughts, world-outlook, goals and relationships in order to understand the text. Nowadays, the term "discourse" became one of the most frequently used terms in the field of linguistics. Looking back to the history, this term was first used by the American linguist Z.Harris in 1952 in his paper entitled "Discourse Analysis".

Naturally, in the occurrence and realization of any speech communication, the participation of three main elements is mandatory: the speaker (or writer), information (text) and listener (reader). In fact, speech condition, means of information, such as voice, writing, magnetic recording, telephone, the status, age and other characteristics of the members of communication, as well as various other non-scientific means play an important role in speech communication. But these three elements are main pillars of speech communication, without any of them the communication process cannot take place. Linguistics, quite naturally, paid primary attention to the issue of linguistic expression and understanding of information, which is the main subject of "giving and receiving" between two parties (speaker, listener) in the

process of communication. After all, the final and main goal of any communication is the “movement” of this information, and this “movement” is through language.

According to the interpretation of uzbek linguist A.Pardaev, discourse is the process in which the speaker and the listener use needed type and form of verbal or non-verbal tool that they consider to be the most effective one to exchange ideas and influence each-other. Discourse can be considered as a process and a type of human activity. It is the process of hundreds of verbal and non-verbal factors’ harmonious realization for an identical aim.

Discourse can be considered from one or two words such as “no smoking” or “stop” to the part of novels that can include more than thousands of words. The volume of discourse lies between the two dimensions mentioned above. [1]

Among western scientists, there are different views on the notion of discourse in literature. The one who utilizes language sources to communicate, have to work with discourse. So, the writer, initially, if the aim is to retell the story or exchange ideas and spread information, should deal with the discourse. In fact, there would not be literature without discourse. However, not all the discourse is the same, and literary scholars divide it into four main types: argument, description, exposition, and narrative. [2]

Argument. The argument is an attempt that convinces the reader through logic and reasoning. The writer makes a specific claim and then provides evidence to support that claim. For example, in academic essays, students use argumentative speech through general thesis to convince the truth.

Description. A description is an emotional experience for the reader that is presented to develop clear mental images of information. For instance, novels, short stories or poems have this power to excite the reader depending on the writer’s strength to do so.

Exposure. The writer informs the viewer about a known fact, but does not seek to influence the audience’s opinion about this fact. Demonstrative speech is neutral in language and tone so as not to persuade the reader or arouse emotions. The purpose is informational only. News stories and more journalistic articles, comparative analyzes and other research-oriented literature usually uses exposition.

Story. A story is a written explanation that presents the story to the reader. In other words, it is the narrator’s voice. The story makes the reader feel and engages and draws the reader to the page through compelling language that

evokes empathy and keeps scrolling. The story is the basis for novels, short stories and some plays.

Other scholars divide the literary discourse into *expressive, poetic and transactional* speech. *Expressive speech* reflects the feelings of the writer. The main focus here is on the development and discussion of ideas and clearly leaves little or no emphasis on facts or arguments that they try to convince. Works of expressive discourse are not always fiction, examples are diaries and journals, blogs and memoirs. *Poetic discourse* is a highly creative approach to artistic writing. Writer presents thoughts, feelings, events, places and characters in imaginative, sometimes rhythmic language that appeals to readers' emotions. In the poetic speech, emphasis is on the topic, image and feelings. This is the central component of poetry, but it also appears in most novels and short stories. *Transactional speech* is less literary, more educational approach. It usually compels the reader to take action and defines a specific action or plan in an active voice. Advertising and marketing records, manuals and business correspondence are considered as common sources of transactional discourse. In scientific sources it is noted that, special scientific conferences were devoted to the solution of this problem. Such scientific researches and different views expressed in relation to the problem of literary discourse indicate that these aspects of linguistics need to be solved.

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